

Metachromasia Induced in Thiazine Dyes by Small Molecules[†]

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Inorganic salts like $[K_4Fe(CN)_6]$, $[K_3Fe(CN)_6]$ and NH_4VO_3 induce distinct but multiple banded metachromasia in more aggregating thiazine dye 1,9-dimethylmethylene blue (DMMB, $2.0 \times 10^{-5} M$) but fail to do so in potentially less metachromatic dye methylene blue (MB). Toluidine blue (TB, $2.0 \times 10^{-5} M$) does not suffer distinct metachromatic shift in presence of these salts. Half-plateau values signifying destruction of metachromatic compounds to the extent of 50% correspond to 12, 8 and 7.50% of ethanol for DMMB- NH_4VO_3 , DMMB- $K_3Fe(CN)_6$ and DMMB- $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ systems respectively. Stoichiometry determination through conductometric titrations reveals that DMMB binds with potassium ferrocyanide, potassium ferricyanide and ammonium metavanadate in the molar ratio of 4 : 1, 3 : 1 and 1 : 1 respectively. Thermodynamic parameters for the dye-salt interactions at different temperatures have been evaluated.

A substrate inducing metachromatic spectral shift of the main absorption band (α -band) of suitable cationic dyes in their dilute aqueous solutions, by facilitating the dye-dye aggregation, is known as a chromotrope. All the cationic dyes are not metachromatic and all the metachromatic dyes are not potentially equal. A metachromatic dye consists of large hydrophobic aromatic portion and small hydrophilic cationic charge centre. Aggregating tendency of a dye increases with the increase of hydrophobic portion of the dye. The greater metachromatic potentiality of dimethylmethylene blue (DMMB) over other members like methylene blue (MB) and toluidine blue (TB) of the same thiazine group has been reported¹⁻³.

A chromotrope is normally polyanionic in nature and its ability depends on anionic charge density and nature of anionic group. Biopolymers like chondroitin sulphates and heparin are good chromotropes¹, and synthetic polyanions like polyvinyl sulphate, polyacrylic acid and polystyrene sulphonate are known⁴ to behave as chromotrope. Chromotropic abilities of inorganic salts like ammonium molybdate⁵ and mercuric chloride⁶ have also been reported.

Though the β -band is said to refer to the dimer band⁷, the aggregation of the minimum number of dye cations required for the exhibition of metachromatic band (μ -band) is yet to be established finally, in fact a uniform generalisation does not seem to fit in all cases since not all cationic dyes are metachromatically alike, nor all the chromotropes behave alike. Czikkley *et al.*⁸ made a theoretical prediction that polyanion having four to six anionic sites would be able to induce metachromasia in a suitable cationic dye. Pal and Mandal² experimentally demonstrated that a polyanion molecule with four anionic sites would induce metachromasia.

In an earlier communication we reported³ the metachromatic interactions of acid polysaccharides of varying

charge densities with different thiazine dyes. We report here the chromotropic abilities of inorganic salts like potassium ferrocyanide, potassium ferricyanide, ammonium metavanadate, potassium persulphate, sodium tungstate and sodium periodate towards thiazine dyes.

Results and Discussion

Figs. 1A, 2A and 3A show the absorption spectra of $2.0 \times 10^{-5} M$, 1,9-dimethylmethylene blue (DMMB) solution in water. Exhibition of prominent dimer band (β -band) around 590 nm in addition to its monomer band (α -band) around 650 nm, reflects strong aggregation tendency of DMMB. DMMB shows distinct but multiple banded metachromasia in presence of $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ (Fig. 1),

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of $2.0 \times 10^{-5} M$ dimethylmethylene blue in (A) water and in presence of $K_4Fe(CN)_6$, (B) $5.90 \times 10^{-5} M$, (C) $11.8 \times 10^{-5} M$ and (D) $17.7 \times 10^{-5} M$.

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Fig 2 Absorption spectra of $2.0 \times 10^{-5} M$ dimethylmethylene blue in (A) water and in presence of $K_3Fe(CN)_6$ (B) $6.0 \times 10^{-5} M$ and (C) $1.5 \times 10^{-5} M$

Fig 3 Absorption spectra of $2.0 \times 10^{-5} M$ dimethylmethylene blue in (A) water and in presence of NH_4VO_3 (B) $4.27 \times 10^{-4} M$, (C) $8.55 \times 10^{-4} M$, (D) $1.28 \times 10^{-4} M$, (E) $1.71 \times 10^{-4} M$ and (F) $2.135 \times 10^{-4} M$

$K_3Fe(CN)_6$ (Fig. 2) and NH_4VO_3 (Fig. 3). Lower concentration of DMMB ($1.0 \times 10^{-5} M$) exhibits broad multiple banded metachromasia in presence of these salts (figure not shown).

Dextran sulphate, heparin and chondroitin sulphate are polyanions of high charge density and are known to induce sharp metachromasia in thiazine dyes DMMB, MB and TB. 'Bael' (*Aegle marmelos*) fruit gum polysaccharide and Bael tree exudate gum polysaccharide³, 'Tal' (*Borassus*

flabellifer) fruit gum polysaccharide⁹ and 'Chalta' (*Dillenia indica*) fruit mucilage polysaccharide¹⁰ are polyanions of relatively lower charge density and are known to induce metachromasia in the stronger metachromatic dye DMMB but not in MB; TB undergoes only modest metachromatic shift in presence of these polyanions.

Metachromatic colour change of a suitable cationic dye is associated with cooperative aggregations of the dye cations. The dye cations are said to be aggregated to dimer, trimer, tetramer and higher multimer¹¹. But generalisation about the aggregation of minimum number of dye cations required for exhibition of metachromatic band (μ -band) can not be made since the magnitude of blue shift of λ_{max} of a dye associated with aggregation depends on the number of dyes aggregated as well as on the distance of separation of monomers and it is also not necessary either.

$K_4Fe(CN)_6$, $K_3Fe(CN)_6$ and NH_4VO_3 induce metachromasia in DMMB but fail to do so in MB. MB, however, has been reported¹² to have stoichiometric binding with $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ and $K_3Fe(CN)_6$. TB, which ranks in between DMMB and MB in metachromatic potentiality, undergoes no distinct metachromatic shift in presence of these salts. Ammonium molybdate has been reported¹² to bind

Fig 4 Plots of absorbance at the α -band of $2.0 \times 10^{-5} M$ dimethylmethylene vs percent ethanol in (A) water and in presence of (B) NH_4VO_3 ($1.282 \times 10^{-4} M$), (C) $K_3Fe(CN)_6$ ($1.51 \times 10^{-4} M$) and (D) $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ ($3.55 \times 10^{-4} M$)

with MB in the molar ratio of 1 : 6 and to induce sharp metachromasia in it, while inositol hexaphosphate fails to induce metachromasia in MB in spite of their stoichiometric binding. Sodium periodate, sodium tungstate and potassium persulphate are also found to cause metachromatic spectral shift of DMMB (figure not shown).

Role of disruptive factor like ethanol over different systems has been studied and the half-plateau values³ signifying destruction of metachromatic compounds to the extent of 50% and hence their stabilities, correspond to 12, 8 and 7.5% ethanol respectively, for DMMB-NH₄VO₃, DMMB-K₃Fe(CN)₆ and DMMB-K₄Fe(CN)₆ system (Fig. 4). Fig. 5A, represents conductometric titration of DMMB (9.6 × 10⁻⁵ M) against K₄Fe(CN)₆ solution (1.18 × 10⁻³ M). This titration curve has two breaks, the first one corresponds to equivalent point and indicates that four DMMB cations are bonded per ferrocyanide ion, while the second one appears at salt concentration twice the equivalent amount. This may be attributed to steric effect¹² suffered by dye ions bound to this anions, and the dye cations redistribute over the less crowded anionic sites, available in presence of excess of the anion. The corresponding stoichiometry for ferricyanide is found to be 3 : 1 dye/anion (Fig. 5B).

Fig. 5. Conductometric titrations plots of dimethylmethylene blue (50 ml, 9.6 × 10⁻⁵ M) with (A) K₄Fe(CN)₆ (1.18 × 10⁻³ M), (B) K₃Fe(CN)₆ (1.51 × 10⁻³ M) and (C) NH₄VO₃ (4.27 × 10⁻³ M).

Vanadate is monoanionic and its interaction with DMMB determined from conductometric titration (Fig. 5C)

is found to be in the 1 : 1 stoichiometry. Now the question of interpretation of the observed blue-shifted metachromasia in suitable cationic dye by vanadate (Fig. 3) naturally arises. The dye cations have the polar ionic groups and the elaborate hydrophobic aromatic parts. Naturally the dyes have strong aggregating tendency and they do exhibit blue-shifted metachromasia even in the absence of any added polyanion at high dye concentration. The factor inhibiting the aggregation in dye cations in dilute aqueous solution is presumed to be the electrostatic repulsion between the dye cations which is partially neutralised at high ionic strength. When a dye cation binds to anionic vanadate with 1 : 1 stoichiometry, the cationic charge of the dye cation is at least partially neutralised, thus facilitating the aggregation of dye cations bound to vanadate anion leading to blue-shifted metachromasia. Such an interpretation has already been expressed by Pal and Pal¹³ relevant to metachromasia of cationic dyes induced by anionic surfactants at concentration much below the critical micellar concentration of the surfactants.

The following model may, therefore, be suggested to metachromasia induced in different cationic dyes by monoanionic chromotrope like vanadate :

where, n need not be a large number and D^+ stands for dye cation.

Table 1 presents the ΔS values calculated from the thermodynamic equations relating K_c , ΔG and ΔS for different systems. Higher negative ΔS value for DMMB-NH₄VO₃ system suggests it to be in more ordered state compared to DMMB-K₃Fe(CN)₆ and DMMB-K₄Fe(CN)₆ systems. This may be attributed to less steric interaction suffered by the dye cations bound to vanadate anions compared to ferricyanide and ferrocyanide anions. This observation is also

TABLE 1—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS FOR INTERACTIONS OF DMMB-K₄Fe(CN)₆, DMMB-K₃Fe(CN)₆ AND DMMB-NH₄VO₃ SYSTEMS

System	Temp. K	K_c	ΔG kcal mol ⁻¹	ΔS cal K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
DMMB-K ₄ Fe(CN) ₆	316	17361	-6.169	
	320	15740	-6.184	-4.2
	323	14166	-6.174	
DMMB-K ₃ Fe(CN) ₆	316	34615	-6.605	
	320	32786	-6.654	-5.0
	323	27027	-6.592	
DMMB-NH ₄ VO ₃	310	1250	-4.42	
	316	714	-4.15	-6.0
	324	681	-4.22	

consistent with the half-plateau values on the basis of disruptive factor like ethanol. The measured free energy changes^{14,15} indicate that the affinity of the salts for the dye DMMB is in the order : $K_3Fe(CN)_6 > K_4Fe(CN)_6 > NH_4VO_3$. This is due to higher potential anionic charge of ferricyanide and ferrocyanide ions compared to vanadate ion and more steric interaction with ferrocyanide than with ferricyanide.

Experimental

Potassium ferrocyanide, potassium ferricyanide, ammonium metavanadate, sodium periodate (E. Merck), sodium tungstate (B.D.H.), potassium persulphate (Sarabhai M.), dimethylmethylene blue (Serva) were used as such, methylene blue and toluidene blue (both E. Merck) were purified through recrystallization¹⁶.

Stock solutions of the dyes DMMB, TB and MB were made in double-distilled water. The dye solutions and other experimental solutions were stored in the dark.

Absorbance was measured with a Toshinwal CL 10A 4 spectrophotometer and conductance with a Systronic 303 conductometer. Stability of metachromatic compounds was studied by recording the absorbances of the metachromatic compounds of different systems and of the dye concerned at the monomer band (α -band) on addition of ethanol in increasing amounts. Stoichiometry was determined by conductometric titrations of the dye, DMMB solution ($9.6 \times 10^{-5} M$) against solutions of $K_4[Fe(CN)_6]$ ($1.18 \times 10^{-3} M$), $K_3[Fe(CN)_6]$ ($1.51 \times 10^{-3} M$) and NH_4VO_3 ($4.27 \times 10^{-3} M$).

Thermodynamic parameters of the dye-salt interactions were determined by measuring spectral changes of the dye-salt mixtures of DMMB- $K_4Fe(CN)_6$, DMMB- $K_3Fe(CN)_6$ and DMMB- NH_4VO_3 systems at their metachromatic band peaks of 555, 540 and 540 nm respectively, under different temperatures (35–50°). The interaction constant (K_c) of the dye-salt system, $D + S \rightleftharpoons DS$, was determined according to the modified equation of Rose and Drago¹⁷,

$$\frac{C_D \cdot C_S}{(A - A_0)} = \frac{L}{K_c L (E_{DS} - E_D)} + \frac{C_S}{(E_{DS} - E_D)}$$

where, C_D is the initial molar concentration of dye, C_S the

initial molar concentration of salt, A_0 the absorbance of the dye-salt mixtures, E_{DS} the molar absorption coefficient of the dye-salt complex, E_D the molar absorption coefficient of the dye, L the length of the light-path and A the absorbance of the dye solution. The value of K_c was calculated from the intercept and slope of the linear plot of $C_D \cdot C_S / (A - A_0)$ vs C_S . Free energy change (ΔG) and entropy change (ΔS) was calculated from the thermodynamic equation relating K_c , ΔG and ΔS .

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